

A Critical Study of the Water Decomposition Product of Ether as well as Ethyl Acetate Extracted Blue Perchromate

Dayal Singh and R. C. Rai

The nature of the water decomposition products of ethereal as well as ethyl acetate extracted blue perchromate has been studied. It has been found to depend on pH and volume of water used to decompose a definite volume of the blue perchromate. It has been shown that when the blue perchromate decomposes in contact with buffer solutions of pH 5.5 or above, the decomposition product is purely $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_8)_3$. The peroxy nature of the product has been established.

Rai and Prakash¹ and Rai² have shown that water decomposition product of ethereal blue perchromate is $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$. A close examination of their data reveals that the said decomposition product is rather a mixture of $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$ and some other compound having a higher oxidising power. Pillai and Rai³ have reported that ethyl acetate extracted blue perchromate decomposes in contact with water to yield $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_8)_3$. It appears quite surprising that the solvent should influence the mode of decomposition of blue perchromate.

From what has been said above, it appears that the nature of the water decomposition product of ether and ethyl acetate extracted blue perchromate has not been thoroughly investigated. The aim of this paper is to investigate the optimum conditions for preparing 100% $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$ and $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_8)_3$.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. *Preparation of the blue perchromate* : Blue perchromate was prepared by mixing ice-cold 0.5 M solutions of CrO_3 and H_2O_2 in requisite volumes. The blue compound thus formed was then extracted with ice cold ether/ethyl acetate, washed with ice-cold distilled water six times and placed in a tightly corked flask in the refrigerator in order to freeze out the water. After about three hours it was transferred to a previously dried and cooled flask surrounded with ice and used for various investigations.

2. *Oxidising power of the blue perchromate* : This was determined in two stages in the following manner :

(A) *Ist stage titration* : To 5 ml. of the blue perchromate was added 5 ml. of 10% aqueous potassium iodide, when iodine was liberated. This was titrated against a standard hypo solution to a yellow end point.

1. R. C. Rai and S. Prakash, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1954, 275, 95.
2. R. C. Rai, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 34, 68; *Journal of the University of Saugar*, 1957, 6.
3. C. V. P. Pillai and R. C. Rai, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 343.

(B) *IInd stage titration* : After the first stage titration was complete, 5 ml. of 2*N* sulphuric acid was added to the yellow solution, more iodine was liberated. This was titrated against the same hypo solution as used in the first stage, to a green end point.

3. *Oxidising power of the water decomposition product of the blue perchromate* : 5 ml. of the same sample of the blue perchromate was allowed to decompose in contact with 10 ml. of water in two flasks separately. After the decomposition was complete, the oxidising power of the contents of one of the two flasks was determined iodometrically in presence of 2*N* sulphuric acid (5 ml.). Then the contents of the second flask were oxidised with 100 vol. hydrogen peroxide (5 ml.) and normal NaOH (5 ml.). The excess of hydrogen peroxide was decomposed by prolonged boiling. The oxidised decomposition product was then titrated iodometrically after it was made distinctly acidic by adding sufficient quantity of 2*N* sulphuric acid. The same hypo solution was used as in the above cases.

4. *Effect of increasing volume of water on the nature of the decomposition product* : Ethereal/ethyl acetate extracted blue perchromate (5 ml.) was allowed to decompose in contact with different volumes of water (see Tables III and IV) in different flasks. After the decomposition was complete, the oxidising power of the contents of each of the flasks was determined as mentioned above.

5. *Effect of pH on the nature of the decomposition product* : Buffer solutions of pH 4.01 and 6.86 were prepared from ready made buffer materials of "Beckman Buffers". Solutions having pH 4.5, 5.0 and 5.5 were prepared by mixing sodium acetate and acetic acid solutions of appropriate molarities. 5 ml. of the ethereal/ethyl acetate extracted blue perchromate was allowed to decompose separately with 10 ml. of each of the buffer solutions. In addition to this 5 ml. of blue perchromate was also decomposed over 10 ml. of a 5% sodium acetate solution. The oxidation value of each of the decomposition products was determined iodometrically.

TABLE I

Oxidising power of ethereal blue perchromate and its water decomposition product.

0.5*M* CrO₃ solution = 10 ml. Hypo solution = *N*/25. Ether = 75 ml.

0.5 *M* H₂O₂ in varying volumes.

Molar ratios CrO ₃ : H ₂ O ₂	Vol. of hypo used in titrating				Ratios	
	Blue perchromate		Water dec. product		b/c e	b/d f
	Ist stage a	IIInd stage b	Unoxidised c	Oxidised d		
1 : 1.0	5.30	7.80	6.60	7.75	1.18	1.0
1 : 1.2	6.75	10.35	8.50	10.30	1.22	1.0
1 : 1.4	7.60	11.30	9.30	11.30	1.21	1.0
1 : 1.6	8.00	11.60	9.60	11.60	1.21	1.0
1 : 1.8	8.80	13.00	11.00	13.05	1.18	1.0

1. The ratios in column 'f' show that oxidation values of second stage titration of the blue perchromate and that of the water decomposition product after oxidation are equal.
2. Ratios in column 'e' lie between 1.18 and 1.22. Ratios obtained by Rai (*loc. cit.*) lie between 1.20 and 1.25.

TABEE II

Oxidising power of ethyl acetate extracted blue perchromate and its water decomposition product

0.5 M CrO₃ solution = 10 ml. Hypo solution = N/25
 0.5 M H₂O₂ varying volumes. Ethyl acetate = 75 ml.

Molar ratios CrO ₃ : H ₂ O ₂	Vol. of hypo used in titrating				Ratios	
	Blue perchromate		Water dec. product		b/c	b/d
	Ist stage	IIInd stage	Unoxidised	Oxidised	e	f
	a	b	c	d	e	f
1 : 1.0	4.20	6.60	5.65	6.65	1.17	1.0
1 : 1.2	4.40	6.80	5.80	6.75	1.17	1.0
1 : 1.4	3.80	5.90	4.90	5.80	1.20	1.0
1 : 1.6	6.65	10.40	8.85	10.40	1.18	1.0
1 : 1.8	8.70	13.70	11.50	13.65	1.19	1.0

The ratios in columns 'e' and 'f' in Tables I and II agree closely. Thus the water decomposition products of ethereal and ethyl acetate extracted blue perchromate appear to be similar. This does not agree with the observations of Rai and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) that ethereal blue perchromate decomposes in contact with water to give Cr₂(Cr₂O₇)₃ and ethyl acetate extracted blue perchromate gives Cr₂(Cr₂O₈)₃.

The difference in the observations may be due to the fact that different workers might have used different volumes of water, for decomposing 5 ml. of blue perchromate. Rai used 20 ml. water, Pillai and Rai used 100 ml. water, while in the present case 10 ml. water was used for this purpose. Consequently 5 ml. of ethereal/ethyl acetate extracted blue perchromate was decomposed in contact with different volumes of water ranging from 10 ml. to 200 ml. The observations made are recorded in Tables III and IV.

TABLE III

Effect of change of volume of water on the nature of water decomposition product of ethereal blue perchromate

0.5 M CrO₃ solution = 10 ml; Ether = 100 ml.;
 0.5 M H₂O₂ = varying volumes; Hypo solution = N/100.

Molar ratios CrO ₃ : H ₂ O ₂	Volume of hypo used in titrating										
	Blue perchromate		Water decomposition product obtained by decomposing blue perchromate over water								
	Ist stage	IIInd stage	10 ml	20 ml	40 ml	60 ml	80 ml	100 ml	120 ml	150 ml	200 ml
	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i	j	k
'A' 1 : 1.0	13.20	21.30	17.10	17.25	17.95	17.65	17.05	16.90	16.35	16.25	16.20
'B' 1 : 1.0	13.40	21.35	17.35	17.60	18.50	18.00	17.20	17.00	16.50	16.30	16.30
'C' 1 : 1.5	18.00	31.05	25.40	25.50	26.25	27.05	26.45	26.30	25.70	23.60	23.65
'D' 1 : 2.0	23.20	38.75	30.90	31.20	32.30	33.00	33.40	33.00	32.50	29.80	29.50

TABLE IV

(Same as for Table III except that ethyl acetate was used instead of ether).

1 : 1.0	13.30	21.40	17.80	18.30	18.80	18.80	19.00	20.00	20.20	19.80	18.20
1 : 1.5	21.20	34.20	28.70	29.70	29.65	30.20	30.20	30.40	31.60	30.00	28.15
1 : 1.5	21.00	33.50	27.40	28.50	28.90	28.85	28.90	29.40	31.30	29.80	28.10
1 : 2.0	27.90	42.40	35.20	36.40	37.30	37.35	37.30	37.30	38.10	37.10	35.50

1. In each series in Table III the oxidation values of the water decomposition product, from left to right, increase at first, become maximum, and then begin to decrease.
2. For 'A' and 'B' series in Table III the maximum oxidation value is in column 'e'. For 'C' and 'D' series the maximum oxidation value is in columns 'f' and 'g' respectively.
3. The ratios, in Table III, b/c and b/d in each series lie between 1.21 and 1.25 and agree with the values of the ratios in column 'e' of Tables I and II. The ratios b/j and b/k lie between 1.30 and 1.33.

In Table IV, the oxidation values of columns 'e', 'f' and 'g' are almost equal. In rest of the columns the trend of the Table III is there.

Maximum oxidation value in each series (Table IV) is in column 'i'.

The ratio b/c in each series (Table IV) agrees with b/c and b/d of Table III and b/c of Tables I and II.

The ratio b/i of Table IV lies between 1.06 and 1.11.

pH measurements of the various decomposition products of series 'A' of Table III were made which are as given below :

column :	'c'	'd'	'e'	'f'	'g'	'h'	'i'	'j'	'k'
pH	3.17	3.25	3.40	3.55	3.60	3.65	3.70	3.75	3.90

From these observations it seems likely that the effect of varying volumes of water on the nature of the decomposition product may be actually due to the pH of the decomposition product. Hence 5 ml. of ethereal/ethyl acetate extracted blue perchromate was decomposed separately in contact with 10 ml. of buffer solutions in different flasks. The observations are recorded in Table V and VI.

It can be seen from Table V and VI that in each case, the oxidation value in column 'c' is the least in each series. It increases from column 'c' to 'f'. The oxidation values in columns 'f', 'g' and 'h' in each series are the same. In both these tables $b/f = b/g = b/h = 1$ for each series. When the decomposition products of columns 'c', 'd' and 'e' were oxidised with 100 vol. hydrogen peroxide (5 ml.) and normal NaOH (5 ml.) and then titrated iodometrically, their oxidation value increased. These titration values were found to be equal to the 2nd stage titration value of the blue perchromate of the respective series.

TABLE V

Effect of pH of the aqueous medium on the nature of the decomposition product of the blue perchromate extracted in ether.

0.5 M CrO₃ = 10 ml; Ether = 75 ml;
 0.5 M H₂O₂ = varying volumes; Hypo solution = N/25.

Molar ratios CrO ₃ : H ₂ O ₂	Volume of Hypo used in Titrating		Water decomposition product obtained by decomposing blue perchromate over 10 ml of					
	Ist stage	IIInd stage	Buffer solutions of pH					5% CH ₃ COONa solution
			4.01	4.5	5.0	5.5	6.86	
	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h
1 : 1.0	5.30	7.80	5.60	6.80	7.10	7.70	7.75	7.70
1 : 1.20	6.75	10.35	7.00	9.20	9.60	10.25	10.25	10.25
1 : 1.4	7.60	11.30	8.30	10.00	10.70	11.25	11.25	11.25
1 : 1.6	8.00	11.60	8.70	10.10	10.90	11.55	11.60	11.55
1 : 1.8	8.80	13.00	9.90	11.40	12.25	13.05	13.00	13.00

TABLE VI

(Same as in Table V except that the blue perchromate was extracted in ethyl acetate)

Molar ratios CrO ₃ : H ₂ O ₂	Volume of Hypo used in Titrating		Water decomposition product obtained by decomposing blue perchromate over 10 ml. of					
	Ist stage	IIInd stage	Buffer solutions of pH					5% CH ₃ COONa solution
			4.01	4.5	5.0	5.5	6.86	
	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h
1 : 1.0	5.95	8.60	6.30	7.70	8.40	8.60	8.60	8.60
1 : 1.2	7.30	10.70	7.50	9.60	10.25	10.70	10.70	10.70
1 : 1.4	8.40	12.80	9.20	11.40	12.10	12.80	12.80	12.80
1 : 1.6	10.00	14.70	10.50	13.10	14.00	14.75	14.70	14.70
1 : 1.8	11.90	17.00	12.50	15.05	16.50	17.00	17.00	17.00

DISCUSSION

Rai (*loc. cit.*) has shown that in the 1st stage titration the blue perchromate decomposed as :

and that in the second stage titration the reaction is :

The oxidising power of Cr₂(Cr₂O₇)₃ can be written as :

From (i) and (ii) it is seen that the ratio of the oxidation values of the second stage titration (i.e., $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_8)_3$ and $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$) is $12/9 = 1.33$. Below Table III, it has been mentioned that b/j and b/k ratios of this table lie between 1.30 and 1.33. Hence ethereal blue perchromate yields almost 100% $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$ only when 5 ml. of this compound are decomposed in a large volume of water.

Pillai and Rai (*loc. cit.*) have reported that ethyl acetate extracted blue perchromate when allowed to decompose in contact with water, yields $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_8)_3$. The oxidation value of this compound is the same as that of the 2nd stage titration of the blue perchromate represented by (ii). Hence ratio of these two oxidation values should be unity. In Table IV none of the decomposition product has oxidation value equal to that of the 2nd stage titration of its series. Hence it is concluded that it is not possible to get 100% $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_8)_3$ by allowing ethyl acetate extracted blue perchromate to decompose in contact with water.

The use of buffer solutions, instead of pure water, has shown better results. From Tables V and VI it can be seen that when blue perchromate, ethereal or ethyl acetate extracted, is allowed to decompose in contact with 5% sodium acetate solution or buffer solutions in the range of pH 5.5–6.86, the decomposition product is 100% $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_8)_3$ which has been found to be quite stable.

Pillai and Rai have claimed that $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_8)_3$ is a peroxy compound like $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$. Its peroxy nature has been established by reacting it separately with dilute sulphuric acid and aqueous potassium iodide solution. The detailed kinetic study of these reactions, since they proceed with measurable speed, is in progress.

Department of Chemistry,
Saugar University,
Sagar (M.P.).

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